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CONTENTS

FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN THE EFFECTIVE ORGANIZATION OF FREE ECONOMIC ZONES.....	51
Mamadiev Elyor	
IMPROVING ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC MECHANISMS FOR THE ESTABLISHMENT AND DEVELOPMENT OF FAMILY GUEST HOUSES	55
Boynazarov Ulugbek Egamberdievich	
IMPROVING METHODS OF ORGANIZING AND DEVELOPING DOMESTIC TOURISM MARKETS IN UZBEKISTAN	61
Daminov Mirvokhid Isroilovich	
THE IMPACT AND SIGNIFICANCE OF INFRASTRUCTURE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE TOURISM SECTOR.....	67
Dilsora Ibodovna Ibodova	
IMPACT OF STUDENTS AGED OVER 40 ON ECONOMIC ACTIVITY AND BUDGETING BASED ON THE COMPETENCY ECOSYSTEM.....	74
Nigora Ikrom qizi Primova	
ОЦЕНКА ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ПРОМЫШЛЕННЫХ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЙ ХОРЕЗМСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ: ЭКОНОМЕТРИЧЕСКОЕ МОДЕЛИРОВАНИЕ И СЦЕНАРНОЕ ПРОГНОЗИРОВАНИЕ НА 2026–2030 ГОДЫ	80
Юсупов Шерзодбек Бахтиёр угли	
IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY FOR ASSESSING THE PROCUREMENT MANAGEMENT SYSTEM IN COMMERCIAL ENTERPRISES.....	87
Ergashev Jahongir Bakhodirovich	
MULTIVARIATE ECONOMETRIC ANALYSIS OF FACTORS AFFECTING HOUSEHOLD INCOME IN SURXONDARYO REGION	93
Abdunazarova Shahnoza Norquchqor qizi	
СРАВНИТЕЛЬНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫХ ЦИФРОВЫХ УСЛУГ АЗЕРБАЙДЖАНА И УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	99
Юсифов Магамед Исмаил оглу, Гасанли Расул Шахин оглу, Белалова Гузаль Анваровна	
SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF THE MINING INDUSTRY IN THE CONTEXT OF THE GREEN ECONOMY.....	105
Xudayberdiyeva Kamila Sadillovayna, Fozilova Zumrad Ahmadovna	
IMPROVING THE ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF CLOTHING MANUFACTURING ENTERPRISES IN UZBEKISTAN THROUGH DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION	111
Axmedova Gaziza Azim kizi	
КОМПЛЕКСНАЯ ОЦЕНКА ПОТЕНЦИАЛА РЕГИОНАЛЬНОГО АГРОПРОМЫШЛЕННОГО ИНТЕГРИРОВАНИЯ НА ОСНОВЕ МОДЕЛИ АНР-TOP SIS	115
Аликулов А.Б.	
APPLICATION OF CLUSTER METHODS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM INFRASTRUCTURE AND IMPROVEMENT OF ECONOMIC MECHANISMS IN SAMARKAND CITY	121
Tashov Mizrob Maxmudovich	
THE ROLE AND PROSPECTS OF THE GREEN ECONOMY IN THE SERVICE SECTOR.....	130
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, Usmonova Dilfuza Ilkhomovna	
FACTORS AFFECTING THE EFFICIENCY OF REGIONAL ENTERPRISES	135
Nigora Zokirjon qizi Toxirova	
CURRENT STATE OF ATTRACTING INVESTMENTS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM IN THE REGIONS OF UZBEKISTAN AND THE METHODOLOGY OF ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY INDICATORS	142
Temurbek Olimovich Mamayunusov	
PRESUPPOSITION SHIFTS IN CROSS-LINGUISTIC RENDERING OF ANECDOTAL NARRATIVES: A COMPARATIVE INQUIRY INTO TRIGGER RETENTION AND TRANSFORMATION	148
Umaraliyeva Dildora Taxirjanovna	

DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES AND RURAL PUBLIC SERVICE QUALITY: AN EMPIRICAL ECONOMETRIC ANALYSIS.....	156
Bek Hunsia, Feruza Mansurovna Ollokulova	
COMPREHENSIVE ANALYSIS OF THE IMPACT OF WOMEN'S LABOR ACTIVITY ON THE EFFICIENCY OF THE ECONOMIC SYSTEM.....	164
Ahrorova Asila Abduaziz qizi	
IMPROVING TAX ADMINISTRATION IN THE ENTREPRENEURIAL ENVIRONMENT.....	170
Azizbek Khurramov	
FORMATION OF FINANCIAL RESULTS AT MOTOR TRANSPORT ENTERPRISES.....	180
Shanazarova Nilufar Baratovna	
ARIMA-BASED ANALYSIS OF SMALL BUSINESS ACTIVITY IN THE AGRICULTURAL SECTOR OF SURKHANDARYA REGION.....	185
Fayziyeva Aziza Azamat qizi	
ASSESSMENT OF AGRARIAN SECTOR EFFICIENCY THROUGH THE SFA MODEL.....	192
Utanov Bunyod Kuvandikovich	
АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫМ ВНЕШНИМ ДОЛГОМ.....	196
Шомуродов Равшан Турсункулович, Жуманазаров Шахобиддин Дилмурод угли	
MODERN METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES TO MANAGING EDUCATIONAL SERVICES MARKETING IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS.....	201
Shamshieva Nargizakhon Nosirkhuja kizi	
FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT OF FOREIGN AND DOMESTIC COTTON GINNING ENTERPRISES: COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS, DIAGNOSTICS, AND IMPROVEMENT DIRECTIONS.....	208
Orif Jumayevich Murodov	
ANALYSIS OF THE INSTITUTIONAL FOUNDATIONS OF STATE INTERVENTION IN THE PRODUCT QUALITY MANAGEMENT PROCESS IN UZBEKISTAN.....	219
Atakulov Askad Raimkulovich	
ИНТЕГРИРОВАННАЯ МОДЕЛЬ ФОРМАЛИЗАЦИИ НЕФОРМАЛЬНОЙ ЗАНЯТОСТИ И РАСШИРЕНИЯ СОЦИАЛЬНОЙ ЗАЩИТЫ В АГРАРНЫХ РЕГИОНАХ (НА ПРИМЕРЕ КАШКАДАРЬИНСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ).....	224
Бобоназарова Юлдуз Ботировна	
THE ECONOMIC ESSENCE OF RESOURCE USE EFFICIENCY AND ITS ROLE IN INDUSTRIAL ECONOMICS.....	229
Baymanova Mavlyuda Djurayevna, Aipova Iroda Ikramovna	
THE ROLE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT: EVIDENCE FROM DEVELOPING COUNTRIES.....	234
Ismatova Diyora Sirojiddin qizi, Ubaydullayeva Gulchexra Erkabayevna	
ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКАЯ УСТОЙЧИВОСТЬ И РЕСУРСНАЯ АДАПТИВНОСТЬ ОТРАСЛИ МАШИНОСТРОЕНИЯ В РОССИИ, КИТАЕ, ИНДИИ.....	239
Викторова Наталья Геннадьевна, Абрамчикова Наталья Викторовна, Ван Байянь	
ENSURING ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC MECHANISMS FOR HOUSING STOCK MANAGEMENT.....	249
Aminova Naima Umar qizi	
STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT FOR ECONOMIC GROWTH: PRACTICAL APPROACHES AND IMPROVEMENTS.....	253
Baymuradov Shokhrukh Makhmudovich, Dilmurodov Komiljon Ahmad o'g'li	
IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF SMALL ENTERPRISES IN THE SERVICE SECTOR (A CASE STUDY OF TASHKENT REGION).....	259
Ashirov Alisher	
IMPROVING THE ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC MECHANISMS FOR THE TRANSFORMATION OF SERVICE ENTERPRISES IN UZBEKISTAN.....	264
Kurbanova Rahima Jamshedovna	
INNOVATIVE IDEAS OF YOUNG ENTREPRENEURS AND INFRASTRUCTURE FACTORS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL INNOVATIVE BUSINESSES.....	270
Ergashev Oybek Khaydaralievich	

MARKETING CHARACTERISTICS OF POSITIONING ORGANIC DRIED FRUIT PRODUCTS IN INTERNATIONAL MARKETS	274
Khidirov Shokhrukh	
TYPOLOGIZATION OF THE ECONOMIC POTENTIAL AND DEVELOPMENT CHARACTERISTICS OF THE DISTRICTS OF SURKHANDARYA REGION BASED ON STATISTICAL AND NEURAL NETWORK APPROACHES.....	280
Normurodov Asliddin Alijon ugli	
THE ROLE OF FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN ANALYSING THE THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE AUDIT OF FINANCIAL LIABILITIES	291
Palvanov Xusniddin Bekimmatovich	
DIGITAL SKILLS AND LABOUR PRODUCTIVITY: A SCENARIO ANALYSIS BASED ON AN INTEGRATED STATISTICAL MODEL	297
Madraimov Xabibulla Madaminovich	
АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ СТРУКТУРЫ АКТИВОВ И ПАССИВОВ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫХ БАНКОВ УЗБЕКИСТАНА	303
Т.И. Бобакулов	
АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ ФИНАНСИРОВАНИЯ ВНЕШНЕТОРГОВУЮ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТЬ КОМПАНИЙ С ДОКУМЕНТАРНЫМИ АККРЕДИТИВАМИ	308
М.Т. Ибодуллаева	
ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ ИНТЕГРИРОВАННОГО МЕХАНИЗМА УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ОСНОВНЫМИ СРЕДСТВАМИ В УСЛОВИЯХ ИННОВАЦИОННОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ	312
Мусаева Жамила Кароматовна	
ПРОБЛЕМНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ КОНКУРЕНТОСПОСОБНОСТИ КОММЕРЧЕСКИХ БАНКОВ УЗБЕКИСТАНА	320
Ш.Т. Ибодуллаев	
THE IMPORTANCE OF STATE SUPPORT AND INVESTMENT POLICY IN ENSURING THE FINANCIAL STABILITY OF MASS MEDIA ENTERPRISES.....	325
Sharipova Shahlo Istamovna	
CURRENT STATUS AND DEVELOPMENT TRENDS OF MOTOR TRANSPORT SERVICES	329
Rakhimov Azamat Hamrakulovich	
ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ ЭКСТРЕМАЛЬНЫХ МОДЕЛЕЙ В ОЦЕНКЕ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО ПОТЕНЦИАЛА ПРЕДПРИЯТИЯ.....	333
Мусаева Шоира Азимовна	
MULTI-FACTOR ECONOMETRIC MODELS OF WATER RESOURCE USE IN ENSURING REGIONAL ECONOMIC STABILITY.....	341
Xaitbaev Jasurbek Otaxanovich	
СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ ПРАКТИКИ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ИНСТРУМЕНТОВ ЭЛЕКТРОННОГО ДОКУМЕНТООБОРОТА В КОММЕРЧЕСКИХ БАНКАХ.....	345
Шомуродов Равшан Турсункулович	
THE WAYS OF IMPROVING COMPETITIVENESS IN COMPANIES OF THE CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRY	350
Buriev Khakim Toshimovich, Usmanov Ixom Achilovich, Tolibov Abduazim Zoxid ugli	
MACROECONOMIC MODELS AND PROSPECTS OF TRANSITION TO A GREEN ECONOMY IN UZBEKISTAN	357
Sharipboyev Hasanboy Marks ugli, Sharipov Kuvondik Baxtiyorovich	
THE IMPACT OF HRM PRACTICES ON ACADEMIC STAFF WORK EFFICIENCY IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS.....	366
Sultonboyeva Munira Bahodirovna, Sultanova Kamila Muktorali Kizi	
THE ECONOMIC ROLE OF RENEWABLE ENERGY SOURCES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE GREEN ECONOMY IN UZBEKISTAN	374
Inatullayeva Intizor Jamshid qizi	
ОЦЕНКА ФИЗИОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ПОКАЗАТЕЛЕЙ КРУПНОГО РОГАТОГО СКОТА, ЗАВЕЗЁННОГО В РЕСПУБЛИКУ КАРАКАЛПАКСТАН ИЗ-ЗА РУБЕЖА, С ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕМ ЦИФРОВЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ.....	378
Аскарова Нилуфар Бахтияровна	

COOPERATIVE MECHANISMS FOR REGIONAL DEVELOPMENT: A FRAMEWORK ANALYSIS OF CULTURAL TOURISM ENTERPRISE PARTNERSHIPS.....	382
Shohrurbek Ruziyev	
IMPROVING THE ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF RESOURCE UTILIZATION IN METALLURGICAL ENTERPRISES: INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE AND MODERN DEVELOPMENT TRENDS	393
Matkuliev Akbar Karimovich	
TAX INCENTIVES GRANTED TO ENTERPRISES LOCATED IN SPECIAL ECONOMIC ZONES	397
Torayeva Nafisa Odiljonovna	
REQUIREMENTS FOR TRANSITIONING TO ELECTRONIC BUSINESS AND CONDITIONS FOR DIGITALIZATION.....	402
Ismoilov Diyorbek Ismoiljon ugli	
DEVELOPMENT OF ALTERNATIVE ENERGY AS AN IMPORTANT FACTOR IN ENSURING A SUSTAINABLE ECONOMY AND ENERGY SECURITY	407
Ergash Bobobekov	
ANALYSIS OF WAGE DYNAMICS IN THE EXAMPLE OF SURKHANDARYA REGION BASED ON PANEL DATA.....	412
Abdunazarova Shahnoza Norquchqor kizi	
THE ROLE OF MARKETING STRATEGIES IN IMPROVING THE MARKET COMPETITIVENESS OF CARPET INDUSTRY ENTERPRISES	420
Arzieva Sevinch Shomurot kizi	
CONSUMER PROPERTIES OF FOOD PRODUCTS IN UZBEKISTAN: TRADITIONS, TRANSFORMATION AND NEW QUALITY STANDARDS.....	425
Gayrat Pardaev	
DIRECTIONS FOR STIMULATING ECONOMIC GROWTH THROUGH THE IMPROVEMENT OF THE TAX SYSTEM.....	431
Yakhshimuratova Khasiyat Khudaybergenovna	
THE ROLE OF E-COMMERCE IN THE ECONOMY OF UZBEKISTAN AND ITS DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS	435
Kambaraliyeva Intizor Suxrobovna	
Aliyarov Olim Abdug'aparovich	
ISSUES OF IMPROVING PRE-TRIAL TAX DISPUTE RESOLUTION MECHANISMS BASED ON INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE	439
Solihova Xumora Xasan kizi	
INCREASING THE ATTRACTIVENESS OF DIVIDEND POLICY IN UZBEKISTAN COMPANIES.....	446
Akmal Komiljonovich Shermukhamedov	
COMMUNITY-BASED HERITAGE TOURISM MODELS AS A TOOL FOR ENHANCING HANDICRAFT DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN	451
Olimjonova Farog'at Dilmurod qizi	
Amiriddinova Muslima Zayniddin qizi	
ИНСТИТУЦИОНАЛЬНЫЕ МЕХАНИЗМЫ СОЦИАЛЬНОЙ ЗАЩИТЫ НАСЕЛЕНИЯ В УСЛОВИЯХ ПЕРЕХОДНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ: ОПЫТ РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН	458
Шоахмедов Шоҳрух Шораҳимович	
OF EFFECTIVE USE OF AGRICULTURAL LAND.....	464
Umarov Muzaffar Yusupbayevich	
ECONOMIC CONTENT OF INTANGIBLE ASSETS IN THE FIELD OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES AND SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS OF THEIR RECOGNITION.....	469
Ishankulov Izzatilla Nurillaevich	
DETERMINANTS OF NON-PERFORMING LOANS IN SERVICE SECTOR LENDING AND CREDIT RISK MITIGATION MECHANISMS.....	473
Nurmukhammedov Abdijabbar Yunusovich	

ESG INTEGRATION PRACTICES INTO CORPORATE CULTURE SYSTEM IN THE JOINTSTOCK SECTOR OF UZBEKISTAN: A CASE STUDY OF “DORI-DARMON” JSC.....	479
Sadikova Muslima Alisher kizi	
DEVELOPMENT OF THE METAL MARKET IN THE TASHKENT REGION AND WAYS TO IMPROVE IT	485
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna	
SMALL BUSINESS AS A CATALYST FOR REGIONAL ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT: AN EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS WITH EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN	491
Jo'rayev Ilhomjon Kamolidinovich	
ISSUES OF DEVELOPING DEPOSIT OPERATIONS IN COMMERCIAL BANKS	497
Rahimov Akmal Matyaqubovich	
IMPROVING TEXTILE LOGISTICS AND SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT IN UZBEKISTAN	503
Isroilov Madaminjon Mukhsinovich	

IMPROVING TEXTILE LOGISTICS AND SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. This article analyzes the theoretical and practical aspects of logistics and supply chain management in the textile industry of Uzbekistan. It examines the existing logistics infrastructure in the industry, the stages of the supply chain, and their impact on economic efficiency. The article also identifies key issues related to logistics costs, the introduction of digital technologies, and export logistics. Based on the research findings, scientifically grounded proposals are developed to improve the logistics system in the textile industry.

Keywords: textile industry, logistics, supply chain, export, digital logistics, transport infrastructure, cluster system.

Аннотация. В статье анализируются теоретические и практические аспекты логистики и управления цепями поставок в текстильной промышленности Узбекистана. Исследуются существующая логистическая инфраструктура отрасли, этапы цепи поставок и их влияние на экономическую эффективность. Также выявлены основные проблемы, связанные с логистическими издержками, внедрением цифровых технологий и экспортной логистикой. По результатам исследования разработаны научно обоснованные предложения по совершенствованию логистической системы в текстильной промышленности.

Ключевые слова: текстильная промышленность, логистика, цепь поставок, экспорт, цифровая логистика, транспортная инфраструктура, кластерная система.

INTRODUCTION

In the global economy, the acceleration of globalization processes, the growth of international trade volumes, and the intensification of competition have made the effective management of logistics and supply chains one of the most pressing issues in production sectors. This is especially important for the textile industry, which is labor-intensive and export-oriented. Timely delivery of products to foreign markets, continuity of raw material supply, and optimization of transport costs are considered key factors in ensuring the competitiveness of enterprises. Therefore, improving logistics systems and effectively managing supply chains are of great importance for the sustainable development of the textile industry.

In Uzbekistan's economy, the textile industry is one of the strategically important sectors. It plays a significant role in increasing the country's export potential, ensuring employment, and producing high-value-added goods. In recent years, large-scale reforms have been implemented in the sector to deepen the processing of cotton fiber, increase the share of finished products, and expand the geography of exports. However, certain issues related to raw material delivery, warehousing, transport logistics, export cargo transportation, and coordination among supply chain participants remain relevant. These factors may affect production efficiency and export competitiveness.

In modern economic conditions, the concept of supply chain management considers the relationships among manufacturers, suppliers, logistics operators, and consumers as a single integrated system. This approach makes it possible to coordinate all stages of product movement, reduce time and costs, use resources efficiently, and satisfy customer needs at a higher level. From this perspective, studying the current state of logistics and supply chain management in Uzbekistan's textile industry and developing directions for its improvement are of significant scientific and practical importance.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Logistics and supply chain management are among the widely studied scientific areas in the global economy. In particular, many studies have been conducted on the importance of logistics in the effective organization of product movement, cost reduction, and the improvement of competitiveness in production sectors. In the textile industry, the complexity and multi-stage nature of supply chains further increase the importance of logistics management.

One of the important scientific approaches in the field of supply chain management was proposed by H. L. Lee (2004). According to Lee, modern supply chains should focus not only on efficiency but also on adaptability and resilience. The author explains supply chain success through the concept of “Agility, Adaptability, and Alignment” (3A). According to this approach, rapid adaptation to market conditions, coordination of participants’ interests, and responsiveness to external changes provide competitive advantage.

D. Ivanov (2021) is one of the scholars who studied the resilience of supply chains. In his view, the COVID-19 pandemic and the global economic crisis demonstrated the vulnerability of supply chains to various risks. Therefore, modern logistics systems should be integrated with risk management mechanisms.

Another important contribution to the field of logistics is reflected in the works of Russell and Taylor (2019). The authors evaluate logistics management as a process that serves the strategic goals of an enterprise and emphasize that reducing logistics costs can help achieve competitive advantage in the market.

Researchers who have studied the efficiency of supply chains in the textile industry note that the shortening of product life cycles and rapid changes in fashion trends require more flexible management of logistics processes. Therefore, the introduction of the “fast supply chain” concept in textile enterprises is of great importance.

Turkish researcher Özlem Bozkurt (2020) studied the relationship between textile exports and logistics infrastructure and argued that the development of transport networks is an important factor in increasing export competitiveness.

One of the fundamental studies in the field of logistics and supply chain management was conducted by the American scientist Douglas Lambert (2008). According to him, supply chain management is the process of creating value by coordinating the activities of all participants, from raw material suppliers to final consumers. Lambert emphasizes that the efficiency of a supply chain is directly related to the level of integration among its participants.

Helena Forslund (2014), one of the scholars who studied the importance of logistics processes in the textile industry, emphasizes the need to use a system of logistics indicators to evaluate supply chain efficiency. Her research indicates that the quality of logistics services and delivery speed have a direct impact on enterprise competitiveness.

Turkish scientist Mustafa Ilter (2018) notes that the development of logistics infrastructure in the textile industry is an important factor in increasing export volumes. In his opinion, integration among the transport system, warehouses, and information technologies significantly reduces the time and costs required for products to reach foreign markets.

Among local scholars, Ghulamov (2019) evaluates logistics as an effective mechanism for managing material and information flows in economic sectors. He notes that the development of logistics systems is important for increasing the competitiveness of the national economy.

Alimov (2020) highlights the growing importance of logistics systems in the context of modernization of the national economy. According to the author, improving logistics infrastructure contributes to the expansion of the country’s foreign economic activity.

Abdurakhmanov (2021), in his studies on the efficiency of labor resources and production processes, emphasizes the impact of logistics systems on the economic performance of enterprises. In his opinion, the optimal organization of resource movement is an important condition for reducing production costs.

Vahobov (2022) analyzes the importance of transport and logistics infrastructure in the development of foreign economic relations and emphasizes that effective use of Uzbekistan’s transit potential can contribute to increasing export volumes.

Mahmudov (2023) examines the cost-effectiveness of supply chain digitalization and notes that digital platforms can reduce logistics costs by 10–15 percent.

Zainutdinov (2021) defines supply chain management as a management concept that integrates production, transportation, and marketing processes. According to the author, the introduction of digital technologies significantly increases the efficiency of logistics processes.

Rasulov (2022) emphasizes that improving export logistics, diversifying transport corridors, and developing logistics centers can strengthen competitiveness in foreign markets.

The analysis of the above scientific approaches shows that logistics and supply chain management are important tools for improving enterprise efficiency, reducing costs, and ensuring competitive advantage. However, the specific features of logistics and supply chain management in Uzbekistan's textile industry, the characteristics of export-oriented production, and the impact of digital technologies on logistics efficiency have not yet been sufficiently studied.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In the course of the research, scientific works of local and foreign scholars in the field of logistics and supply chain management, reports of international organizations, relevant regulatory and legal documents, and statistical data related to the textile industry were analyzed. Methods of analysis and synthesis were used in studying the scientific literature, comparing the theoretical views of different authors, and forming general conclusions related to the research area. This made it possible to determine the scientific and theoretical foundations of logistics process management in the textile industry.

The comparative analysis method was widely used in the study. Through this method, the current state of logistics processes and supply chains in Uzbekistan's textile industry was compared with international experience. In addition, the statistical analysis method was applied in the practical part of the research. The main economic indicators of the industry were examined based on data from the Statistics Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, textile industry enterprises, and official industry-related sources.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

World practice shows that in a modern economy, the competitiveness of enterprises is determined not only by production volume and product quality, but also by the effectiveness of supply chain organization. This is especially important in industries with multi-stage production processes, such as the textile industry, where the efficiency of the logistics system directly affects product costs, export volumes, and the financial performance of enterprises.

In recent years, the establishment of cotton-textile clusters in Uzbekistan has created a vertically integrated chain from raw material production to finished product manufacturing. This, in turn, has increased the need to apply new models of supply chain management. However, practice shows that high logistics costs in the sector, long transport distances to foreign markets, and the incomplete implementation of digital logistics solutions have limited the sector's export potential to a certain extent.

In order to analyze the movement process of textile products, the main structural elements of the supply chain were systematized in Table 1.

Table 1
Functional structure of the supply chain of the Uzbek textile industry¹

A link in the supply chain	Main task	Value to be created
Cultivation of raw cotton	Formation of the raw material base	Primary value
Fiber processing	Production of cotton fiber	Added value
Yarn production	Preparation of semi-finished products	Value addition
Gas production	Creating a basis for the finished product	High value
Sewing and knitting products	Production of finished products	Highest value
Logistics services	Transportation and storage	Store value
Export and sales	Delivery to the final consumer	Commercial value

Table 1 shows that the main share of product value is formed at the stages of processing and finished goods production. However, in the process of bringing this value to foreign markets, a certain portion may be lost due to the inefficiency of the logistics system. Therefore, optimizing logistics processes is an important condition for ensuring product competitiveness.

Uzbekistan's geographical location has a significant impact on foreign trade logistics. The country's lack of direct access to seaports creates additional transportation costs when exporting products to foreign markets. This is especially relevant for finished textile products exported to the European Union and North American markets.

¹ author's development

In order to evaluate the factors affecting logistics processes, the following systematization was carried out based on the analysis of industry experts' opinions and scientific literature (Table 2).

Table 2
Factors affecting the efficiency of logistics in the textile industry²

Factor	Impact level	Effect on performance
Transport infrastructure	Up	Reduces delivery time
Availability of logistics centers	Up	Reduces warehouse costs
Digital technologies	Up	Accelerates information flows
Customs processes	Average	Affects export time
Personnel capacity	Average	Increases the quality of management
Transportation tariffs	Up	Affects cost formation
International logistics cooperation	Up	Allows access to new markets

As noted above, transport infrastructure and digital technologies are among the most important components of the logistics system. In particular, the digitalization of information exchange among supply chain participants ensures transparency in product movement and increases the speed of decision-making.

The analysis shows that enterprises that implement digital supply chain technologies gain greater opportunities to monitor product movement, plan inventory, and control logistics costs. As a result, excess inventory decreases and the efficiency of working capital utilization increases.

The results of the analysis also indicate the need to further develop transport and logistics centers in the country. Logistics centers make it possible to centralize the processes of product consolidation, storage, redistribution, and preparation for export. This, in turn, can significantly reduce logistics costs for small and medium-sized textile enterprises.

The textile industry of Uzbekistan is an important component of the country's industrial production and has strategic importance in generating export revenues. As a result of structural reforms implemented in the sector in recent years, the transition from raw cotton exports to the production of finished goods has been expanding. This makes improving the efficiency of supply chain management and logistics systems an important economic task (Table 3).

Table 3
Dynamics of Uzbek textile exports

Year	Export volume (billion USD)	Share of total exports (%)
2021	3.0	18.9
2022	3.1	15.7
2023	3.2	13.4
2024	2.9	10.6

Source: Compiled by the author based on data from the Statistics Agency of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

An analysis of the dynamics of Uzbekistan's textile exports shows that the sector's position in foreign markets has been steadily strengthening. In particular, in 2023, the country's textile exports reached USD 3.2 billion, almost doubling compared with 2016. By the end of 2024, export volume amounted to approximately USD 2.87–2.90 billion, accounting for 10.6 percent of the country's total exports.

The table shows that, although export volumes remained high, their share in the overall export structure decreased slightly. This can be explained by increased competition in foreign markets, rising transport costs, and disruptions in international logistics chains.

From the supply chain perspective, the process of textile products entering foreign markets consists of several functional stages (Table 4).

² author's development

Table 4
Key links in the Uzbek textile industry supply chain³

Step	Process	Main task
1	Cotton cultivation	Formation of the raw material base
2	Cotton processing	Fiber preparation
3	Yarn production	Preparation of semi-finished products
4	Gas production	Creating added value
5	Sewing and knitting products	Production of finished products
6	Warehouse and logistics	Storage and distribution
7	Export logistics	Delivery to foreign markets

In 2024, Uzbekistan exported 496 types of textile products to more than 50 countries. In the export structure, yarn and thread products accounted for 43–47 percent, while finished textile products accounted for 37–39 percent. This indicates that products with relatively low added value still represent a significant share of the export structure.

The analysis shows that logistics costs constitute a significant part of the total cost of exporting textile products. Uzbekistan's lack of direct access to seaports increases transportation costs in foreign trade operations. As a result, delivery times to European and American markets are longer compared to those of competing countries.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The analysis indicates that Uzbekistan's textile industry has developed a multi-stage supply chain that extends from cotton production to the delivery of finished products to foreign markets. However, the limited development of transport infrastructure, significant dependence on transit routes when accessing international markets, relatively high logistics costs, and the incomplete implementation of digital logistics solutions continue to affect the sector's export potential.

The research findings reveal a direct relationship between logistics efficiency and export competitiveness. Reducing logistics costs contributes to lower product costs, shorter delivery times, and greater capacity to meet customer demand in foreign markets. In addition, the implementation of digital supply chain technologies enhances product tracking, inventory management, and the efficient utilization of resources.

Based on the results of the study, the following recommendations are proposed:

First, it is advisable to further develop the transport and logistics infrastructure supporting textile exports. This includes expanding the network of modern logistics centers, multimodal transport terminals, and export-oriented warehousing facilities.

Second, digital logistics technologies should be more widely introduced in textile enterprises. In particular, the adoption of ERP (Enterprise Resource Planning), SCM (Supply Chain Management), and WMS (Warehouse Management System) solutions can accelerate information exchange among supply chain participants and improve the effectiveness of management decisions.

Third, in order to reduce transportation costs in export logistics, it is important to diversify international transport corridors and strengthen regional logistics cooperation. This will not only improve access to foreign markets but also enhance the stability and reliability of export operations.

Fourth, the system for training highly qualified specialists in supply chain management should be further improved. Expanding cooperation between higher education institutions and manufacturing enterprises can contribute to the preparation of professionals with modern logistics knowledge and practical skills.

Fifth, it is advisable to increase the level of integration among supply chain participants within textile clusters. Stronger coordination between raw material suppliers, manufacturers, and distributors can improve overall operational efficiency and supply chain performance.

In conclusion, improving the logistics and supply chain management system in Uzbekistan's textile industry is one of the key factors for further increasing the sector's export potential, strengthening the competitiveness of textile products in international markets, and supporting the country's sustainable economic growth.

³ author's development

REFERENCES

1. Ballou, R. H. *Business Logistics/Supply Chain Management*. 5th ed. New Jersey: Pearson Education, 2007.
2. Bozkurt, Ö. "Logistics Infrastructure and Export Competitiveness in the Textile Industry." *Journal of Transportation and Supply Chain Management*, vol. 14, no. 1, 2020.
3. Bruce, M., & Daly, L. *Fashion Supply Chain Management*. London: Routledge, 2018.
4. Forslund, H. *Performance Management in Supply Chains*. Lund: Lund University Publications, 2014.
5. Ilter, M. *Logistics Management and Textile Industry Competitiveness*. Istanbul: Istanbul Commerce University Press, 2018.
6. Ivanov, D. "Supply Chain Viability and the COVID-19 Pandemic." *International Journal of Production Research*, vol. 59, no. 12, 2021, pp. 3534–3552.
7. Lambert, D. M. *Supply Chain Management: Processes, Partnerships, Performance*. Florida: Supply Chain Management Institute, 2008.
8. Lee, H. L. "The Triple-A Supply Chain." *Harvard Business Review*, vol. 82, no. 10, 2004, pp. 102–112.
9. Russell, R. S., & Taylor, B. W. *Operations and Supply Chain Management*. New York: Wiley, 2019.
10. Abdurakhmanov, Q. X. *Effective Utilization of Resources in the Context of Economic Digitalization*. Tashkent, 2021.
11. Alimov, R. A. *Development of Logistics Systems in the Context of Modernization of Uzbekistan's Economy*. Tashkent: Iqtisodiyot, 2020.
12. Vakhobov, A. A. *International Economic Relations and Transport Logistics*. Tashkent, 2022.
13. Gulomov, S. S. *Fundamentals of Logistics*. Tashkent: Fan va Texnologiya, 2019.
14. Zainutdinov, Sh. N. *Logistics and Supply Chain Management*. Tashkent: Iqtisodiyot, 2021.
15. Mahmudov, N. M. "Economic Efficiency of Implementing Digital Logistics Systems." *Economy and Education*, No. 5, 2023.
16. Rasulov, A. A. "Issues of Developing Export Logistics in the Textile Industry of Uzbekistan." *Economy and Innovative Technologies*, No. 4, 2022.

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